

**ASSESSMENT OF MEDICATION DISPENSING ERRORS AND THEIR
CONTRIBUTING FACTORS IN COMMUNITY PHARMACY PRACTICE SETTINGS
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ABSTRACT

Background: Medication dispensing errors are a significant patient safety concern in community pharmacy practice. **Aim:** To assess medication dispensing errors and their contributing factors among community pharmacists in Cuddalore, Tamil Nadu. **Methods:** A prospective cross-sectional study was conducted among 108 registered community pharmacists using a validated structured questionnaire distributed through direct survey and Google Forms. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including chi-square test and one-sample t-test in MS Excel, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant. **Results:** Among the participants, 59.43% were aware of medication dispensing errors, while 53.77% identified look-alike/sound-alike drugs as high-risk medications. Most pharmacists agreed that preventive measures and error reporting improve pharmacy practice. Major contributing factors included lack of double-checking systems, similar drug names, and frequent interruptions during dispensing. **Conclusion:** Community pharmacists demonstrated moderate to good knowledge and positive attitudes toward medication dispensing errors. Strengthening double-checking systems, medication safety training and workflow management may help reduce dispensing errors and improve patient safety.

KEYWORDS: Medication dispensing error, Community pharmacy, Pharmacist practice, Medication safety.**1. INTRODUCTION**

Medication dispensing errors are recognized globally as one of the most significant threats to patient safety in healthcare systems. Medication errors can occur during prescribing, transcribing, dispensing, administration, and monitoring processes.^[1] Among these, dispensing errors are particularly important because pharmacists serve as the final checkpoint before medications reach patients. Any error during dispensing may lead to adverse drug reactions, therapeutic failure, increased healthcare costs, prolonged hospitalization, and reduced patient trust in healthcare services.^{[2][3]}

Medication dispensing errors refer to deviations occurring during the interpretation, preparation, packaging, labeling, and supply of prescribed medicines

to patients.^[4] These errors include wrong drug dispensing, incorrect dosage strength, and wrong dosage form, wrong quantity, labeling mistakes, omission errors, and dispensing medicines to the wrong patient.^[5] Dispensing errors may arise due to human factors, system-related failures, communication gaps, high workload, poor prescription clarity, and interruptions during dispensing.^[6]

Community pharmacies are among the most accessible healthcare settings and serve as an essential source of healthcare services, especially in developing countries.^[7] Community pharmacists are increasingly involved in patient counseling, medication review, chronic disease management, and medication safety practices. However inadequate staffing, look-alike/sound-alike medications,

and lack of structured reporting systems can increase the risk of medication dispensing errors.^[8]

Worldwide studies have shown wide variations in the prevalence of dispensing errors. Research from different countries has identified high workload, poor communication, illegible prescriptions, lack of double-checking systems, and environmental distractions as common contributors to medication dispensing errors. Despite growing awareness regarding medication safety, underreporting of dispensing errors remains a major challenge in pharmacy practice.^[9]

In India, particularly in regional community pharmacy settings, limited studies are available regarding pharmacists' knowledge, attitudes, practices, and factors associated with medication dispensing errors. Understanding pharmacists' perceptions and practices is important for identifying gaps and implementing preventive interventions.^[10]

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

A cross-sectional study was conducted over a period of 3 months among registered community pharmacists practicing in selected community pharmacies across Cuddalore District, Tamil Nadu. The study population consisted of registered pharmacists working in community pharmacy settings.

Sample Size

The sample size was calculated using the Raosoft sample size calculator with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. The final sample size was determined to be 108 participants.

Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection, and participant confidentiality was maintained throughout the study.

Study instrument

The study instrument consisted of a structured and physician-validated questionnaire developed in accordance with the objectives of the study. The questionnaire contained 26 questions divided into five sections, covering demographic characteristics, knowledge, attitude, practice, and factors associated with medication dispensing errors among community pharmacists. The questionnaire was designed to assess pharmacists' knowledge, attitude, practice, and factors related to medication dispensing errors.

Inclusion Criteria

- Registered community pharmacists.
- Pharmacists willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Hospital pharmacists.
- Pharmacies managed by non-professionals.

- Participants unwilling to participate.

Data Collection Procedure

The structured questionnaire was distributed directly to community pharmacists and through Google Forms. Participants were informed about the objectives of the study, and informed consent was obtained before data collection.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were entered and analyzed using Microsoft Excel. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to summarize the data. Inferential statistical tests, including the chi-square test and one-sample t-test, were performed to determine statistical significance. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DEMOGRAPHIC DETAILS OF CONSENT

The entire question from the questionnaire provided the information need to frame the results.

Table No. 1: Consent.

CONSENT	PERCENTAGE
Agree	91.66%
Disagree	8.33%

Fig. 1: Responders of Consent.

Table 1 shows a total of 108 community pharmacists participated in the study. Among them, 99 responded to the questionnaire, yielding a response rate of 91.66%.

DEMOGRAPHIC DETAILS OF GENDER

Table No. 2: Gender.

GENDER	PERCENTAGE
Male	61.32%
Female	22.64%
Prefer not to say	10.00%

Fig. 2: Gender.

Table 2 presents the gender distribution of the respondents based on self-reported data obtained from

Educational Qualification

Fig. 3: Educational Qualification.

Table 3 summarizes the educational qualifications of the respondents as obtained from the questionnaire. The respondents were categorized based on their qualifications as D.Pharm 60 (56.60%), B.Pharm 24(22.64 %), Pharm.D 10 (9.433 %), and M.Pharm 5(4.71%). Figure 3 depicts the percentage distribution of educational qualifications among the respondents.

the questionnaire. Among the respondents, 65 (61.3 %) were male and 24 (22.64 %) were female. Figure 2 illustrates the gender characteristics of the respondents.

DEMOGRAPHIC DETAILS OF EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION

Table No. 3: Educational Qualification.

EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION	PERCENTAGE
D.Pharm	56.60%
B.Pharm	22.64%
Pharm.D	9.43%
M.Pharm	4.71%

DEMOGRAPHIC DETAILS OF YEARS OF EXPERIENCE

Table No. 4: Years of Experience.

EXPERIENCE	PERCENTAGE
<1year	21.69%
1-5years	55.66%
6-10years	10.37%
>10years	5.66%

Fig. 4: Years of Experience.

Table 4 presents the distribution of respondents according to their years of experience in community pharmacy practice, based on self-reported questionnaire data. Respondents were categorized into four groups:

less than 1 year 23 (21.69 %), 1–5 years 59 (55.66 %), 6–10 years 11 (10.37 %), and more than 10 years 6 (5.66 %). Figure 4 illustrates the percentage distribution of respondents across the experience categories.

KNOWLEDGE TOWARDS MEDICATION DISPENSING ERROR**Table No. 5: Knowledge towards medication dispensing error.**

S.NO	QUESTIONS	NUMBERS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Are you aware of the term "Medication dispensing error"? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Not sure	63 12 24	59.43% 11.32% 22.64%
2.	Which of the following is considered as a medication dispensing errors? <input type="checkbox"/> Dispensing an incorrect drug <input type="checkbox"/> Dispensing medicine without patient counseling <input type="checkbox"/> Dispensing a medicine to the wrong patient <input type="checkbox"/> Dispensing medicine after an interruption or distraction	54 11 16 18	50.94% 10.37% 15.09% 16.98%
3.	Which category of medicines may require extra caution during dispensing? <input type="checkbox"/> Over-the-counter medicines <input type="checkbox"/> Vitamin supplements <input type="checkbox"/> Look-alike/Sound-alike drugs <input type="checkbox"/> Herbal products	25 11 57 6	23.58% 10.37% 53.77% 5.66%
4.	What is the main purpose of reporting dispensing errors in pharmacy care settings? <input type="checkbox"/> To reduce the occurrence of dispensing errors <input type="checkbox"/> To meet administrative requirements <input type="checkbox"/> To enhance patient safety <input type="checkbox"/> To improve quality of pharmacy care	17 10 64 8	16.03% 9.43% 60.37% 7.54%
5.	Which situations can increase the possibility of a dispensing error? <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear prescriptions <input type="checkbox"/> Unorganized storage of medicines <input type="checkbox"/> Frequent interruptions during dispensing <input type="checkbox"/> Dispensing medicines without double-checking	14 14 42 29	13.20% 13.20% 39.62% 27.35%

Table No. 6: Hypothesis Testing (Count).

Aware of the term Medication dispensing error	Category of medicines may require extra caution during dispensing				Total
	OTC	Vitamin supplements	Look-alike/Sound alike drugs	Herbal products	
Yes	17	1	45	0	63
No	0	4	2	6	12
Not sure	8	6	10	0	24
Total	25	11	57	6	99

Table No. 7 Chi-Square Tests.

Tests	Value	df	Asymp.Sig.(2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	49.72 ^a	6	<0.001
Likelihood Ratio	52.83	6	<0.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	18.41	1	<0.001
No of Valid Cases			99

Chi-square analysis was performed to assess the association between awareness of medication dispensing errors and medicines requiring extra caution. Since the p-

value was statistically significant, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was accepted.

ATTITUDE TOWARDS MEDICATION DISPENSING ERROR**Table No. 8: Attitude towards medication dispensing error.**

S.NO	QUESTIONS	NUMBERS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Community pharmacists should take adequate steps to reduce dispensing errors.		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree	66	62.26%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Disagree	17	16.03%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Not sure	16	15.09%
2.	Faster dispensing should be prioritized even if it increases the risk of errors.		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree	26	24.52%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Disagree	59	55.66%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Not sure	12	11.32%
3.	Mandatory double-checking would significantly reduce dispensing errors.		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree	57	24.52%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Disagree	9	8.49%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Not sure	33	31.13%
4.	Reporting medication dispensing errors helps to improve future pharmacy practice.		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree	76	71.69%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Disagree	9	8.49%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Not sure	12	11.32%
5.	Medication dispensing error is a normal occurrence in pharmacy settings.		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree	23	21.69%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Disagree	65	61.32%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Not sure	11	10.37%

(Hypothesis Testing) Table No. 9 One-Sample Statistics.

Statement	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Standard Error Mean
Adequate steps to reduce dispensing errors	99	2.494949	0.774251	0.0778
Mandatory double-checking to reduce dispensing errors	99	2.484848	0.660297	0.0664

Table No. 10: One-Sample Test.

Statement	Test	df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Adequate steps to reduce dispensing errors	6.36	98	< 0.001	0.494949	0.341	0.649
Mandatory double-checking to reduce dispensing errors	7.30	98	< 0.001	0.484848	0.353	0.617

Hypothesis testing showed statistically significant differences regarding adequate steps and mandatory double-checking to reduce medication dispensing errors.

Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was accepted.

PRACTICES TOWARDS MEDICATION DISPENSING ERROR**Table No. 11: Practice towards medication dispensing error.**

S.NO	QUESTIONS	NUMBERS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Do you review drug–drug interactions before dispensing?		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Always	76	71.69%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes	14	13.20%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Never	9	8.49%
2.	Do you provide medication counseling to patients at the time of dispensing?		

	<input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Never	61 30 8	57.54% 28.30% 7.54%
3.	Is the expiry date of medicines verified prior to dispensing? <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Never	54 35 10	50.94% 33.01% 9.43%
4.	Do you clarify unclear prescriptions before dispensing medicines? <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Never	71 16 12	66.98% 15.09% 11.32%
5.	Do you dispense medicines without re-checking after an interruption? <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Never	21 24 54	19.81% 22.64% 50.94%

(Hypothesis Testing) Table No. 12 One-Sample Statistics.

Statement	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Standard Error Mean
Review drug – drug interactions before dispensing	98	2.626	0.722	0.072
Clarify unclear prescriptions before dispensing	98	2.555	0.758	0.076

Table No. 13: One-Sample Test.

Statement	Test	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Review drug–drug interactions before dispensing	8.63	98	0.000	0.626	0.48	0.77
Clarify unclear prescriptions before dispensing	7.28	98	0.000	0.556	0.40	0.71

Hypothesis testing showed statistically significant differences in reviewing drug–drug interactions and clarifying unclear prescriptions before dispensing.

Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was accepted.

FACTORS TOWARDS MEDICATION DISPENSING ERROR

Table No. 14: Factors towards medication dispensing error.

S.NO	QUESTIONS	NUMBERS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Which factor is most likely to contribute to dispensing errors in community pharmacies? <input type="checkbox"/> High work load and time pressure <input type="checkbox"/> Lack of effective double-checking <input type="checkbox"/> Interruptions during dispensing <input type="checkbox"/> Staff shortage	24 53 18 4	22.64% 50.00% 16.98% 3.77%
2.	Which system-related factor can reduce dispensing errors in community pharmacies? <input type="checkbox"/> Decreased workload <input type="checkbox"/> Following standard operating procedures <input type="checkbox"/> Implementation of double-check system <input type="checkbox"/> Reduced interruptions during dispensing	11 26 56 6	10.37% 24.52% 52.83% 5.66%
3.	Which factor is associated with patient that can increase the chance of dispensing errors? <input type="checkbox"/> Incomplete available of patient medication history <input type="checkbox"/> Communication barrier between patient and pharmacist <input type="checkbox"/> Use of multiple medicine (polypharmacy)	15 24 52	14.15% 22.64% 49.05%

	<input type="checkbox"/> Insufficient time for patient consultation with pharmacist	7	6.60%
4.	Which factor is most commonly associated with mechanical errors in pharmacy dispensing?		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Inadequate time for patient counseling	17	16.03%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Similar drug names	60	56.60%
	<input type="checkbox"/> High workload	12	11.32%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Insufficient therapeutic training	10	9.43%
5.	Frequent interruptions from the surrounding environment can lead to:		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Decreased accuracy in dispensing	19	17.92%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Increased number of dispensing errors	56	52.83%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Less patient interaction	13	12.26%
	<input type="checkbox"/> Reduce Faster dispensing	11	10.37%

(Hypothesis Testing)**Table No. 15: Count.**

Years of experience	Factor is most commonly associated with mechanical Errors in pharmacy dispensing				Total
	Inadequate time for patient counseling	Similar drug names	High workload	Insufficient therapeutic training	
<1year	4	13	5	1	23
1-5years	8	46	3	2	59
6-10years	3	1	3	4	11
>10years	2	0	1	3	6
Total	17	60	12	10	99

Table No. 16: Chi-Square Tests.

Tests	Value	Df	Asymp.Sig.(2-sided)
Pearson Chi Square	39.62 ^a	9	<0.001
Likelihood Ratio	41.08	9	<0.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.54	1	0.011
No of Valid Cases	99		

Chi-square analysis was performed to assess the association between years of experience and factors contributing to mechanical dispensing errors. Since the result was statistically significant, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was accepted.

4. CONCLUSION

The present study concluded that community pharmacists demonstrated moderate to good knowledge and positive attitudes toward medication dispensing errors. However, dispensing errors were still influenced by workload, interruptions, inadequate double-checking systems, polypharmacy, and look-alike/sound-alike medications. Strengthening medication safety programs, pharmacist training, standard operating procedures, error reporting systems, and communication among healthcare professionals is essential to reduce dispensing errors and improve patient safety in community pharmacy practice.

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